

Whole consortium together again at AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024 at Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria Industrial de Barcelona (UPC)

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From June 18 to 20, 2024, at the Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria Industrial de Barcelona (ETSEIB - UPC), the summer meeting of the [AGRIGEP project](#) (Assessment and implementation of Agriculture and Life Science Universities' first Gender Equality Plans in widening countries) was held.

Project Background and Scope

The AGRIGEP project, funded by Horizon Europe, creates a collaborative environment for co-designing gender equality actions and activities at partner universities with the support of experienced mentors. This initiative is part of a broader effort to ensure that gender equality is not only envisioned but actively integrated into the teaching and administrative frameworks of European universities.

Meeting Summary

During three days the 6 partners of the AGRIGEP project the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) (*Hungary*) - project coordinator, the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU) (*Czech Republic*), the University of Primorska (UP) (*Slovenia*), Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE) (*Hungary*), Yellow Window (YW) (*Belgium*), and the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC) (*Spain*) have met to share information and experiences, as well as to plan and discuss the evolution of the project.

Visit Highlights:

- **June 18:** During the 1st day of the AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024 at UPC [mid-project meeting](#) was held in hybrid format, where all 6 partners of the project met.
- **June 19:** After Ice-Breaking Session, the Vice-Rector for Social Responsibility and Equality of the UPC, Josefina Antonijuan, welcomed the attendees and explained the actions in the field of gender equality at the UPC in recent years.
- **June 20:** The last day of the Summer Meeting was June 20 and among other activities was a session on "Data Monitoring Systems" with the participation of the Office of Planning, Evaluation and Quality (GPAQ). In the session "Gender-Based Violence" 2 students of the Feminist Assembly of the ETSEIB gave presentations.

Key Points

- **Main Topics:** Project status updates, report discussions, stakeholder engagement, institutional organization, participation techniques, career development, feminist assembly, and reflections from workshops.
- **Interactive Sessions:** Ice-breaking, 'Ask Marcela', and Resistances sessions.

Expert insights and participant feedback

Dr Rosó Baltà Salvador (UPC) summarized her experience from the meeting: *'This week, we hosted the Summer School of the Horizon Europe project AGRIGEP at the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya. More than 20 participants from various countries attended the event, including Slovenia, Hungary, the Czech Republic, and Belgium. The gathering proved to be incredibly enriching. We engaged in various talks, interesting discussions, and workshops that utilized design thinking techniques to address gender equality issues within university institutions. It was particularly fascinating to see tools like archetypes, use cases, and empathy maps applied in the context of equality. This week's sessions have reinforced our commitment to creating a more equitable academic environment!'*

Conclusion

The AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024, successfully brought together the consortium's six partner institutions for three days of productive collaboration and insightful discussions. Overall, the AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024 reinforced the consortium's dedication to embedding gender equality into the teaching and administrative frameworks of European universities. The event was a significant step forward in the project's mission to co-design and implement effective gender equality plans, ensuring a more inclusive and equitable future for higher education institutions.

AGRIGEP Beneficiaries:

WIDENING PARTNERS

- Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE), **Coordinator**
- Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)
- University of Primorska (UP)

MENTORING PARTNERS

- Yellow Window (YW)
- Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NATE)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC)

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